

MONOCOTYLEDONOUS PLANTS OF THE FLORA OF THE SURKHAN STATE RESERVE INCLUDED IN THE RED BOOK

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Abstract. In the article, The Surkhondarya region (Boysun, Kohitang Flora) is located in the southern region of our country information on the endemic and rare family, the list of 150 species of plants belonging to the category, their biological characteristics, distribution area and ecology, as well as the reasons for their decline. As a result of field research and analysis techniques, rare and endemic single-ball gazelles of the flora of the Surkhon State Reserve have been reported as well as globally important plant species under threat of extinction.

Key words: flora, kohitang, tree, unicorn poaceae., ridge, mountain-forest, ecosystem and endemic.

ОДНОДОЛЬНЫЕ РАСТЕНИЯ ФЛОРЫ СУРХАНСКОГО ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО ЗАПОВЕДНИКА, ЗАНЕСЕННЫЕ В КРАСНУЮ КНИГУ

Аннотация. В статье Сурхандарьинская область (Бойсунская, Кохитангская флора) расположена в южном регионе нашей страны, сведения об эндемичных и редких семействах, перечень 150 видов растений, относящихся к категории, их биологические особенности, ареал распространения. и экологии, а также причины их упадка. В результате полевых исследований и методов анализа были зарегистрированы редкие и эндемичные джейраны флоры Сурхонского государственного заповедника, а также глобально важные виды растений, находящиеся под угрозой исчезновения.

Ключевые слова: флора, кохитанг, дерево, единорог злаковый, хребет, горно-лесной, экосистема и эндемик.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the growth of the world population, the expansion of the areas used for agricultural crops, changes in the infrastructure of places as a result of the construction of residential complexes and production facilities, the development of oil and gas and other fossil industries have a negative effect on the diversity of herpetofauna. Especially, due to the destruction of natural landscapes, the reduction of habitats of wild animals leads to the reduction of their number and the extinction of vulnerable species [1, 5].

Accordingly, in order to preserve herpetofauna, a component and resource of biological diversity, in the conditions of anthropogenic transformation, it is of great scientific and practical importance to assess the condition of amphibian and reptile populations and to determine their trends of change, to develop measures for the protection of rare and endangered species.

In our republic, special attention is paid to the preservation of the environment and biological diversity, which is important for sustainable development, and to ensure the stability of the ecosystem. In this regard, measures were developed, including ensuring the stability of natural ecosystems, protecting rare and endangered species of animals.

The flora of the Surkhan oasis includes 150 species belonging to 41 families and 78 genera, which are considered rare and relict, as well as endemic species. Today, these species are protected in Surkhan State Reserve, Boysun and Hisar Forestry. But even in unprotected areas there are endemic plant species included in the Red Book of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Studying the current state of their population and the reasons for their decline is considered one of the urgent problems [3, 5].

Surkhandarya region is surrounded by the Kohitang range in the west, Boysun in the north, the southern slope of the Hisar range in the northeast, and the lower part of the western slopes of Bobotog in the east. Its southern border passes through Amudarya. The territory of the province is divided into Boysun, Kohitang and Bobotog botanical geographic regions [3, 6].

The mountains surrounding the Surkhandarya region from the west, north and east prevent air masses from passing into the region in both summer and winter. That is why the region is the hottest country in our republic (annual average temperature +170 C). Summers are dry and hot, winters are mild and warm, so subtropical plants can grow. The average temperature in January is +10, +40 C. But sometimes the winter months become much colder, and the lowest temperature drops to -200, -270 C. The average temperature in July is +280, +320 C, and the highest temperature is +42 +480 C. In the city of Termiz, the temperature even rises to +500 C in summer.[2]

According to the research results, 545 genera and 1435 species of plants belonging to 92 families were brought. Of these, 119 species of endemic plants of the Kohitang ridge with different statuses have been studied and are being researched.

METHODS

Rare and endemic species of Surkhandarya region were identified as a result of field research and laboratory practice.

1.Family: *Asphodelaceae*

Category: *Eremurus* M.Bieb.

Species: *Eremurus albertii* Regel. - Albert Shirach

In Uzbekistan is a rare species, 25-80 tall perennial grass up to cm. Rhizome shortened, claw-like, the lobes are strongly thickened, 7-10 mm thick. The leaves are wide pencil, of the outer side width 1.5-2 cm. Shingles are sparse, many-flowered, 10-50 cm long. Flowered leaves are large, triangular- rascally. Below the ball florets are 2-2.5 times longer than the peduncle. Rose petals are one veined, reddish-red, elongated towards the base. Skiers 1.5 times shorter than saffron. The pod is round, three-celled, smooth, 2-2.5 wide cm. It blooms in April and bears fruit in May.

Distribution area. In the Sherabad lowland of the Kohitang ridge, 900-1200 m above sea level in the Kadik mountains as well as in the Bobotog ridge it grows sparsely and scattered in rocky terrain at altitude.

The composition of the flora of the Surkhan reserve, located on the eastern slope of the Kohitang ridge, was studied, and it was found that it consists of 743 species belonging to 77 families and 372 genera. The flora of the reserve was analyzed according to taxonomy, areology, biomorphology, ecology, and its distribution along the steep regions was studied. A comparative analysis was made with the flora of Nurota and Chotkal

reserves, which have the same administrative status. In the composition of the flora, 22 species of endemics of the Kohitang range were found. 5 of them are endemic to the reserve [5, 154-156].

Species: *Emurus baissunensis* O. Fedtsch.

A perennial herb 60-80 cm tall, a highly reduced endemic plant in South-Western Pamir-Oloy. The rhizome is short, 4-6 mm wide. The leaves are pencil-thin, 4-6 mm wide. Shingles are sparse, many-flowered, 25-45 cm long. Floral leaves are large, triangular in shape. The flower clusters at the bottom of shingil are 1.5 times longer than those of the flower. The flowers are fragrant. Cauliflower leaves are white, single-veined. The wings are uneven and shorter than the rosary.

Distribution area. On average, 10-12 plants grow in an area of 100 m² in rocky, small gravel-stone, gypsum lands around Boglidara, Tangi-Dara and Khatak villages of the Kohitang range (at an altitude of 1000-1200 m above sea level). It is distributed in the Machaydarya basin of the Boisun ridge, in the foothills and lowlands of the Upper Machai, Kok bet, Khalkajar, Kumarik regions.

RESULTS

In the article, the study of the floristic composition of the Surkhan State Reserve as a result of the field research conducted in the Kohitang mountain range of Sherabad district serves as the basis for all future scientific research, as well as creating the opportunity to develop measures for the systematic protection of its rich and diverse plant resources. The rare flora of the Surkhan State Reserve and the following from endemic monocots. 22 species of endemic and subendemic taxa (2.96% of the total flora) of the Surkhan State Reserve are distributed in mountain regions, 4 species (0.54%) in pastures, and 1 species (0.13%) in hilly regions. It is known that the main part of endemic plants is distributed in the mountain region of the reserve. According to their life forms, 12 species of endemic plants (1.61% of the total flora) belong to polycarpous grasses, 3 species to semi-shrubs (0.40%), 2 species (0.27%) to biennial grasses [6, 1563].

CONCLUSION

The flora of the Surkhan oasis includes 150 species belonging to 41 families and 78 genera, which are considered rare and relict, as well as endemic species. Today, these species are protected in Surkhan State Reserve, Boysun and Hisar Forestry. But even in unprotected areas there are endemic plant species included in the Red Book of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Studying the current state of their population and the reasons for their decline is considered one of the urgent problems. For this, it is necessary to carry out explanatory work among tourists, tourists and local residents who go to rest in the heart of nature.

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